

DIVERSE HEALTH CONSEQUENCES ASSOCIATED WITH DIETARY PATHOGENS- OVERVIEW

D.K Shanmuganathan*, M. Mukil, DR. G. Ariharasivakumar

Department of Pharmacology, KMCH College of Pharmacy

Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R Medical University, Chennai.

ABSTRACT

Even though foodborne parasitic diseases have the potential to harm human health seriously, they are frequently disregarded in various food safety control systems, because of the output and financial losses connected to them. They are tough to detect because they are frequently invisible and, the infected animals often exhibit no symptoms. Pork, fish, vegetables, water, freshwater crustaceans, and the surrounding environment can all expose humans to proper hygiene, farming, and fishing methods, and by raising community awareness, the risks connected to all of them can be reduced. Due to these pathogens, people are facing severe health consequences that lead to the spread of various diseases. This study involves control measures and the treatment of these illnesses

Keywords: Neurocysticercosis, Chagas heart disease, miscarriage, clonorchiasis, cystic echinococcosis

1.INTRODUCTION

The correlation between food consumption and human diseases was identified at an early stage, with Hippocrates (460 B.C.) noting a robust association between ingested food and the manifestation of human illnesses. Foodborne illness transpires when a pathogenic organism is consumed with food and subsequently establishes, often undergoing multiplication, within the human host. Alternatively, it may arise when a toxigenic pathogen colonizes a food product, giving rise to the production of toxins that are subsequently ingested by the human host [1-3]

In instances, of food-borne infections, a prolonged incubation period is typically implicated, resulting in a considerably extended duration between ingestion and the manifestation of symptoms as compared to food-borne intoxications. In numerous nations, oversight for averting human exposure to certain food-borne parasites lies within the purview of either veterinary authorities or food safety agencies. Conversely, in some regions, comprehensive control measures are absent for foodborne parasites. An inherent challenge stems from the

asymptomatic nature of infection in affected animals, posing difficulties for both farmers and regulatory bodies in promptly detecting and addressing such issues. According to estimates from the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), one in six Americans, or about 48 million people, will become ill each year as a result of coming into contact with a foodborne pathogen. An estimated 128,000 hospital admissions and 3,000 fatalities result from this. Eight common agents are responsible for the majority of foodborne illnesses, hospitalizations, and fatalities.

- *Campylobacter*
- *Staphylococcus aureus*
- *Toxoplasma gondii*
- Norovirus
- Nontyphoidal salmonella
- *Clostridium perfringens*
- *Listeria monocytogenes*
- *E. coli*, commonly known as STEC, is a bacterium that produces a toxin called Shiga toxin.

E. coli is commonly categorized into STEC, exemplified by *E. coli*, and non-Shiga toxin-producing, encompassing enteropathogenic, enteroinvasive, enteroaggregative, and diffusely adherent *E. coli*. The landscape of foodborne pathogens continually evolves, with new entities emerging while others diminish or disappear. The ability to predict the emergence or disappearance of specific pathogens, apart from identified outbreaks, remains challenging and has not significantly curtailed or prevented foodborne illnesses. Human parasitic infection results vary greatly based upon several factors, including the host's health, the infection site, the length of the incubation period, the species, strain, or genotype of the parasite, its dosage, and its life stage. The manifestation of clinical illness resulting from parasitic infections is contingent upon several variables, such as the immune capacity of the afflicted person and the unique traits of the parasitic agent. Days to weeks may pass between the onset of mild to severe clinical presentations, or they may manifest as protracted neurological and developmental pathology. Such long-term outcomes may encompass organ dysfunction, morphological deformities, or fetal loss. Notably, parasitic infections have the propensity to endure throughout the host's lifespan, and the availability and efficacy of treatments are subject to variability based on the particular species, parasite stage, and site of infection.

Fig 1: FAO/WHO ranking of terrestrial and aquatic meat-borne zoonotic parasites by importance for socioeconomic impact and international trade. Parasites include those that are common globally or regionally

PARASITES	ENVIRONMENTAL STAGES OF THE LIFE CYCLE	STAGES OF LIFE CYCLE IN ECTOTHERMIC HOSTS	SOURCES OF INFECTION IN HUMAN
Nematodes			
<i>Anisakids</i>	+	+	Marine mammals; marine fish and squid
<i>Ascaris</i> spp.	+	-	Pigs and environment
<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	+	-	People; environment
Cestodes			
Diphyllobothridae	+	+	Piscivorous mammals and birds & copepods & freshwater/marine fish
<i>Spirometer</i> spp.	+	+	Mammals copepods; freshwater crustaceans and fish and various
Trematodes			
Heterophyidae	+	+	Piscivorous mammals snails & fresh/brackish water fish
Opisthorchidae	+	+	Piscivorous mammals, snails; freshwater fish
Paragonimus spp.	+	+	Piscivorous mammals &; snails &; freshwater crustaceans

Table 1: Life cycles of various parasites and their sources [4]

2. EPIDEMIOLOGY OF FOODBORNE DISEASES [5-6]

Globally, foodborne illnesses constitute a significant public health challenge, contributing substantially to elevated morbidity and mortality rates.

- The worldwide prevalence of infectious diarrhea encompasses an estimated 3-5 billion cases annually, resulting in nearly 1.5 million deaths.
- In the United States, foodborne diseases contribute to approximately 48 million cases of illness, leading to 128,000 hospitalizations and 3,000 fatalities annually
- If the existing condition of food safety standards endures in India, it is estimated that there will be more than 100 million annual instances of foodborne diseases. This number is expected to rise to a range of **150–177 million cases by the year 2030.**
- Tissue infections originating from foodborne parasites often manifest with insidious, prolonged, and heightened pathogenic characteristics. Instances of such maladies linked to contaminated food encompass,
- Myalgia from *Trichinella* in pork and horse meat, gastric ulceration brought on by *Anisakids* in fish, and neurocysticercosis from *T. Pork* contains sodium; produce causes hydatidosis from *Echinococcus*; fish causes cholangiocarcinoma from *Clonorchis sinensis* and *Opisthorchis viverrine*; and aquatic plants cause bowel duct blockage from *Fasciola*

HEALTH IMPACTS	SOURCES OF INFECTIONS	CESTODES	TREMATODES	NEMATODES	PROTOZOA
Taeniasis, neurocysticercosis	Pig 	<i>Tenia Solium</i>	-	<i>Trichinella spp</i> (also in other meats)	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> (also in other meats)
Cholangiocarcinoma Liver enlargement	Freshwater fish 	-	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i> , <i>Opisthorchis viverrine</i>	-	-
Pulmonary Tuberculosis, lung cancer	Freshwater crustaceans 	-	<i>Paragonimus spp</i>	-	-
Cholangiocarcinoma	Marine fish 	-	-	<i>Anisakis spp</i>	-
Fascioliasis	Vegetables, and the Environment 	<i>Taenia Solium</i> , <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> , <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i> , <i>Fasciola gigantica</i>	<i>Ascaris spp</i>	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> , <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> , <i>Entamoeba histolytica</i> .

Table 2: Major foodborne and waterborne parasites in Asia ⁴

3. HEALTH IMPACTS CAUSED BY FOOD-BORNE PARASITES

3.1 NEUROCYSTICERCOSIS

A parasite infection at the larval stage is known as cysticercosis. The fecal-oral infection of humans with *T. Solium* eggs from tapeworm carriers causes cysticercosis. It is of various forms,

- ❖ Extraneural cysticercosis
- ❖ Ophthalmic cysticercosis
- ❖ Neurocysticercosis

Neurocysticercosis is the main condition that can affect people mainly through the ingestion of **uncooked meat, especially pork**. The parasite typically invades the central nervous system, giving rise to neurocysticercosis. Cysticerci, once they enter the central nervous system, do not die and cause very little tissue inflammation. With the blood-brain barrier acting as a barrier, cysticerci can remain in this stage for a while.[7]

SYMPTOMS

- Seizures.
- Headaches.
- Nausea,
- vomiting
- confusion (cysticercal encephalitis).
- Stiff neck

Neurocysticercosis most commonly manifests as epileptic seizures, which are typically the only or primary sign of the illness. In patients with parenchymal brain cysts or calcifications, seizures appear in 50–80% of cases; however, they are less common in other disease presentations. When a neurological examination is performed, most of these people show normal results. Of a group of patients with neurocysticercosis who initially present with seizures, about half go on to develop recurrent seizures suggestive of epilepsy. This group of patients mostly had mild infection manifestations. This syndrome is associated with the **positioning of parasites** within the cerebral ventricles or basal cisterns, impeding the circulation of cerebrospinal fluid. It arises from **various mechanisms**, including

- ❖ The direct presence of the parasite
- ❖ Inflammation of the ependyma or
- ❖ Residual fibrosis.

When massive cysts, typically measuring more than 1-2 cm, press against nearby cerebral structures, localized impairments and intracranial hypertension result. Most often, cyst enlargement takes place inside the basal cisterns or in the subarachnoid space around the Sylvian fissure. In addition, edema resulting from cyst degeneration or a stroke exacerbating neurocysticercosis can cause motor impairments. Compared to intraparenchymal infections, strokes are more common in subarachnoid neurocysticercosis. When endarteritis affects small penetrating arteries, they mainly appear as deep lacunar infarcts; large vessel occlusion is an uncommon complication. [8-10]

Approximately 1% of neurocysticercosis cases result in spinal compromise, characterized by compressive manifestations. Cysts predominantly reside in the subarachnoid space, with intramedullary cysts being an infrequent occurrence.

LIFE CYCLE OF TAENIA SOLIUM

Fig 2: Life cycle of *Taenia solium*

Fig 3: Taenia solium cysts in pork brain.

Fig 4: Taenia solium cysts in a human brain.

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF NEUROCYSTICERCOSIS

According to WHO, Neurocysticercosis (NCC) stands as the predominant preventable etiology of epilepsy on a global scale, purportedly contributing to approximately 30% of epilepsy incidences in regions endemic to the parasite. Within certain populations, the correlation between NCC and epilepsy may escalate to as high as 70%.

Nonetheless, according to recent CT and MRI scans, the incidence of NCC is startlingly high in India, particularly in the poorer, meat-eating segments of the population who either don't receive treatment at all or have a treatment gap of more than 90%. [10]

Fig 5: Global epidemiological status of neurocysticercosis

SOURCE -THE LANCET NEUROLOGY

DIAGNOSIS

1. SEROLOGY

Neurocysticercosis is suspected based on the presence of eosinophils in the cerebrospinal fluid. *Hymenolepis nana* and *Echinococcus granulosus*, two common cestode infections, commonly cause cross-reactivity in the ELISA test. A positive antibody test in patients with calcified cysticercosis alone is a common finding and should not be interpreted as indicating the presence of live parasites. The enzyme-linked immunoblot assay was originally reported to have a sensitivity of 98 percent and a specificity of 100 percent. Antigen detection assay can identify live parasites, which helps guide treatment choices and oversight.

NEUROIMAGING

For the diagnosis of neurocysticercosis, radiography has always been essential. The key characteristics are the quantity, size, and location of lesions. First, soft tissue and skull radiographs showed calcifications; later diagnostic procedures such as arteriography and pneumoencephalography showed lesions causing hydrocephalus and mass effect; these methods are now deemed dangerous and out of date for this indication. These days, the most common methods for diagnosing neurocysticercosis are CT and MRI. It has been reported that CT has a sensitivity and specificity of more than 95%. Cysts manifest as regions of reduced density within imaging scans, exhibiting distinct boundaries, frequently accompanied by a denser protrusion within, indicative of the presence of the parasite's scolex. In advanced phases, the cyst adopts a density comparable to the surrounding tissue, yet becomes discernible post-contrast administration, displaying enhanced characteristics resembling either a nodular or ring-like structure. Termed as an enhancing lesion or cysticercus granuloma, this image is minimally apparent in pre-contrast images, indicative of the later degenerative stage.

MRI is the most accurate technique to assess the degree of infection, the location, and the evolutionary stage of the parasites. It visualizes well perilesional edema and the degenerative changes of the parasite, as well as small cysts or those located in the ventricles, brainstem, cerebellum, eye, and basal racemose vesicles.

Absolute criteria include

- Histological demonstration of the parasite,
- Cystic lesions with scolex on neuroimaging, or
- Direct visualization of ocular cysts.

TREATMENT

Numerous investigations suggest that **albendazole**, administered at a conventional dosage of **15 mg/kg/day** in two divided doses over **15 days**, may exhibit migliore efficacy compared to **praziquantel (at a dosage of 50 mg/kg/day for 15 days)** in the treatment of neurocysticercosis. Through comparative clinical trials, albendazole has been shown to either match or surpass praziquantel in reducing the number of viable cysticerci.

Furthermore, current findings from a placebo-controlled, double-blinded trial indicate that albendazole treatment (at a regimen of 400 mg twice daily alongside 6 mg of dexamethasone once daily for 10 days) significantly reduces the occurrence of generalized seizures over a 30-month follow-up period.

Treatment of symptoms has an important role in the management of neurocysticercosis. Seizures generally respond well to first-line antiepileptic drugs. [11-12]

CONTROL AND PREVENTION

In endemic areas, control measures should concentrate on the pork tapeworm carrier, environmental tapeworm eggs, diseased pigs, strict meat inspection, and education. It is thought that putting pork in the freezer for at least 14 days at -10°C will effectively eradicate T's infectious potential. *Solium cysticerci*. If slaughterhouse inspections stop the sale and consumption of contaminated pork, transmission can also be stopped.

In Mexico, the efficacy of health education interventions in isolation has been investigated, yielding promising yet partial outcomes. While there was a notable enhancement in disease-related knowledge, behavioral practices associated with either increased or decreased risk (such as hand hygiene, open defecation in agricultural areas, and pig husbandry practices) showed no significant alteration.

Anthelmintic chemotherapy programs have a better chance of long-term success when they are incorporated into a larger intersectoral strategy to raise public awareness and encourage hygiene practices. Other strategies to maintain the effects of particular interventions include the supply of clean water and sanitation, health education about parasite transmission, and methods of enhancing human and animal hygiene.

3.2 CHAGAS HEART DISEASE

INTRODUCTION

Chagas cardiomyopathy was defined in patients who tested serologically positive for *Trypanosoma* and had at least typical symptoms of heart disease such as electrocardiogram abnormalities. It's caused by the protozoa *Trypanosoma*. Chronic Chagas cardiomyopathy is characterized by early left anterior bundle branch block or right bundle branch block. It progresses to severe ventricular arrhythmias, which can lead to heart failure.

Certain patients face an unfavorable prognosis and are predisposed to fatal arrhythmias and heart failure, necessitating thorough prognostic evaluation of this condition. Specialists advocate for risk assessment in all individuals with chronic Chagas disease. The Research

identified diminished left ventricular function and New York Heart Association (NYHA) cardiac functional classification at Grade 3 or 4 as indicators of an adverse prognosis in Chagas cardiomyopathy. The distinctive myocardial fibrosis exhibited pathologically in Chagas cardiomyopathy is a feature that distinguishes it from other cardiomyopathies [13-15]

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

It includes,

- Bradyarrhythmia,
- Tachyarrhythmia,
- Cardioembolic events,
- Heart failure (hf), and
- Sudden death

LIFE CYCLE OF TRYPANOSOMA CRUZI

Fig 6: Life cycle of *Trypanosoma cruzi*

SOURCE: Center for Disease Control And Prevention

CLASSIFICATION

There are mainly five different classifications,

- The Kuschnir classification
- The Brazilian Consensus on Chagas Disease
- The modified Los Andes classification
- The Latin American Guidelines
- The American Heart Association

1. THE KUSCHNIR CLASSIFICATION

CLASSIFICATION	ECG	XRAY/CARDIAC SYMPTOMS
0	Normal ECG findings	Normal heart size
I	Abnormal ECG findings	Normal heart size
II		Left ventricular enlargement
III		Congestive heart failure

2. THE BRAZILIAN CONSENSUS ON CHAGAS DISEASE

CLASSIFICATION	ECG	ECHOCARDIOGRAM	HF
A	Abnormal	No LV wall motion abnormalities	No
B1	Abnormal	LV wall motion abnormalities with LV ejection fraction (LVEF) $\geq 45\%$	No
B2	Abnormal	LV wall motion abnormalities with LVEF $<45\%$	No
C	Abnormal	LV wall motion abnormalities	Compensated HF
D	Abnormal	LV wall motion abnormalities	Refractory HF

3. MODIFIED LOS ANDES CLASSIFICATION

CLASSIFICATION	ECG	ECHOCARDIOGRAM	HF
IA	Normal	Normal	No
IB	Normal	Abnormal	No
II	Abnormal	Abnormal	No
III	Abnormal	Abnormal	Yes

4. LATIN AMERICAN GUIDELINES

CLASSIFICATION	ECG/X-RAY	ECHOCARDIOGRAM	HF
A	No structural heart disease (normal ECG and chest X-ray)	-	No
B1	ECG changes (arrhythmias or conduction disorders)	Mild contractile abnormalities with normal LVEF	No
B2		Decreased LVEF	No
C		Decreased LVEF	Prior or current symptoms of HF
D		-	Symptoms of HF at rest, refractory to maximized medical therapy (NYHA functional class IV)

5. AMERICAN HEART ASSOCIATION

CLASSIFICATION	ECG/ Echocardiogram	HF	DIGESTIVE CHANGES
A	Normal ECG	Neither structural cardiomyopathy nor HF symptoms	No
B1	Structural cardiomyopathy evidenced by ECG or echocardiographic changes with normal LVEF	Neither current or previous signs and symptoms of HF	-
B2	Structural cardiomyopathy characterized by decreased LVE	Neither current or previous signs and symptoms of HF	
C	LV systolic dysfunction	Current or previous symptoms of HF (NYHA functional class I, II, III, or IV)	
D	LV systolic dysfunction	Refractory symptoms of HF at rest despite optimized clinical treatment requiring specialized interventions	

POSSIBLE MECHANISMS [16-18]

1. Parasite-Induced Myocytolysis

One of the earliest and most prominent theories to explain myocarditis caused by *Trypanosoma cruzi* infection, based on the observation of parasites in inflamed tissue, suggested that chronic inflammation was a reparative mechanism to mitigate the mechanical damage caused by the parasite. The absence of parasite pseudocysts in tissue samples collected from the majority of deceased individuals with chronic Chagas heart disease (CHD) has traditionally posed a challenge in establishing a direct correlation between *Trypanosoma cruzi* infection and the progression of chronic CHD pathology. Using PCR analysis, Belotti et al. detected *Trypanosoma cruzi* in 69% of 16 patients diagnosed with chronic Chagas heart disease (CHD). They observed parasite antigen in over 70% of myocardial tissue sections showing moderate to severe myocarditis, whereas it was found in less than 17% of areas with mild or absent myocarditis.

In 1999, Zhang and Tarleton introduced a novel immunological assay aimed at indirectly detecting antigens and genetic markers of *Trypanosoma cruzi*. This technique was based on the precise localization of the parasite's kinetoplast DNA (kDNA) within the tissue samples of individuals suffering from chronic Chagas heart disease (CHD). Utilizing this method, which is noted for its high sensitivity, they discovered a clear link between the ongoing presence of the parasite within the body and the occurrence of inflammation in the tissues. Simoes-Barbosa et al. later found evidence that the horizontal transfer of *T. cruzi* mitochondrial DNA to the genomes of naturally infected humans via integration into LINE-1 retrotransposons may play an important role in the pathogenesis of CHD.

2. Primary Neuronal Damage

As early as 1922, Chagas and Vilella documented signs of autonomic dysfunction in patients infected with *Trypanosoma cruzi*, indicating the presence of dysautonomia in congenital heart disease (CHD). Koberle proposed that the main mechanism behind cardiac pathogenesis in Chronic Chagas Heart Disease (CHD) was intramural denervation. This hypothesis was based on his examination of heart sections from patients who had died from chronic Chagas disease, using a consistent method to count the intramural neurons. Several inconsistencies have persistently diminished the relevance of this hypothesis. These discrepancies encompass the nuanced and fluctuating nature of cardiac denervation in congenital heart disease (CHD) patients as well as the absence of a connection between the degree of denervation and the cause of death or the pathological features observed in the heart.

3. Damage to Cardiac Microvasculature

In chronic congenital heart disease (CHD) patients, cardiac tissue displays localized areas of myocyte death alongside the formation of reparative interstitial fibrosis. These pathological features closely resemble those observed in the experimental framework of ischemia and reperfusion due to temporary disruptions in microvascular blood flow.

POSSIBILITIES

1. In the experimental framework of congenital heart disease (CHD), various microcirculatory anomalies leading to ischemia were detected in infected mice. These anomalies include the presence of occlusive thrombi and platelet aggregates within small epicardial and intramural

coronary arteries. Additionally, focal vascular constriction and notable structural irregularities such as dilation, altered deposition of extracellular matrix, and proliferation of microvessels were observed. These phenomena could arise from vascular endothelial cell damage induced either directly by *T. cruzi* or immune effector cells or as a result of the inflammatory infiltrate. Furthermore, *T. cruzi* infection triggers the production of endothelin-1, a potent vasoconstrictor, from infected endothelial cells, potentially exacerbating myocardial ischemia by reducing circulatory capacity.

2. Another possibility is that microvascular damage may be indirectly initiated by the parasite, as it has been shown that *T. cruzi* calreticulin, which helps the parasite evade the host immune system by modulating the complement system, also inhibits angiogenesis *in vivo*.

3. Additionally, *T. cruzi* produces several bioactive lipids such as thromboxane A and prostaglandin F₂ α which are potent vasoconstrictors that also promote vascular permeability, vascular smooth muscle cell proliferation, and platelet aggregation

4. Antibody-mediated Cytotoxicity and Non-Specific Damage Caused by Eosinophils and Neutrophils

Infiltration of inflammatory cells is a hallmark feature of the cardiac problem observed in both acute and chronic congenital heart disease. The infiltration of leukocytes predominantly comprises lymphocytes, with a lesser presence of macrophages, eosinophils, plasma cells, neutrophils, and mast cells. Immunohistochemical methods later confirmed the presence of activated eosinophils and the accumulation of components from eosinophil granules in deteriorating cardiac lesions.

Cardiac harm that includes bystander cell harm might also encompass antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC). ADCC, showcased by the activity of mononuclear cells, eosinophils, and neutrophils against the bloodstream form of *Trypanosoma cruzi* trypomastigotes, has been evidenced in mouse models

Antibodies tethered to parasites can potentially mobilize cytotoxic effector cells toward cardiac lesions, heightening the likelihood of tissue harm induced by granulocyte constituents. This process adds to the injury inflicted by autoreactive antibodies. It's noteworthy that antibody-mediated injury has been documented to precipitate extracardiac pathologies in individuals with chronic Chagas disease, including mesangial glomerulopathy arising from hypersensitivity (type III) responses characterized by the deposition of *T. cruzi*-specific antibodies within the renal parenchyma.

It is feasible that certain compounds synthesized by *T. cruzi* possess significant cytotoxicity towards cells within the living organism. An instance of this is an acid-active hemolysin released by *T. cruzi*, referred to as TC-Tox, which shares an immunological resemblance with the human complement protein C9.

5. Toxin Secretion by the Parasite

It is conceivable that certain compounds synthesized by *T. cruzi* possess notable cytotoxic properties within living organisms. One such instance is the presence of an acid-activated hemolysin termed TC-Tox, which is antigenically akin to the human complement factor C9.

Andrews and his team have suggested that this protein plays a role during the invasion of cells, possibly facilitating the breakdown of the phagosome membrane that houses the parasite shortly after it invades. Additionally, a protein called LYT1, which has a similar size to TC-Tox and reacts to anti-C9 antibodies, indicates a structural likeness

POSSIBLE MECHANISM UNDERLYING PROGNOSIS OF ChHD AND POTENTIAL THERAPEUTIC TARGETS [19]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

In recent decades, shifts in emigration patterns from Chagas-endemic regions have significantly impacted the epidemiological landscape of this disease in non-endemic regions such as the United States. For instance, Bern and Montgomery estimated in 2009 that approximately 300,000 individuals residing in the United States are afflicted with chronic *T. cruzi* infection. Individuals who test positive for Chagas disease antibodies typically have the indeterminate, asymptomatic form of the disease and are often unaware of their infection. However, they still pose a potential risk of transmitting the disease to others. The consideration of Chagas disease in immunocompromised patients, notably organ transplant recipients, has gained prominence. Unrecognized infection among blood and organ donors poses a potential risk of transmitting the infection through transfusion or transplantation. However, rigorous screening programs for blood donors in the United States, Canada, and endemic regions have effectively minimized the risk of transfusion-transmitted infection. [20-24]

Fig 7: Global epidemiological status of Chagas heart disease

DIAGNOSIS

Patients diagnosed with Chagas disease should undergo clinical evaluation and an electrocardiogram (ECG) to diagnose Chagas heart disease (CHD). In instances of coronary heart disease (CHD), it is imperative to assess the extent of myocardial engagement, prognosticate clinical outcomes with a focus on mortality risk stratification, and commence pharmacotherapeutic interventions. Patient education should be incorporated as an integral component of comprehensive patient care. The initial diagnostic evaluation of individuals with coronary heart disease (CHD) includes a comprehensive assessment of their medical history, physical examination, as well as gathering epidemiological and social data.

Specifically, the analysis of B-type natriuretic peptides (BNP and NT-ProBNP) can serve as a valuable tool in diagnosing heart impairment in patients with suspected clinical symptoms and in determining prognosis. In primary care settings where ECG results are normal, echocardiography may not be obligatory. However, in the presence of ECG abnormalities, echocardiography and Holter monitoring become necessary. Echocardiography plays a pivotal role in the assessment and monitoring of patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) owing to its widespread availability, portability of equipment, and comprehensive diagnostic capabilities. It enables the staging of CHD patients, detection of risk, and facilitates follow-up and risk assessment. Echocardiography allows for the evaluation of chamber dimensions, global and regional left ventricular (LV) contractility, presence of LV aneurysms, LV diastolic function, left atrial (LA) size and function, and right ventricular (RV) systolic function. Moreover, it serves as a valuable tool in identifying concurrent non-CHD conditions that may contribute to clinical symptoms and/or electrocardiographic abnormalities.

TREATMENT

In the treatment of Chagas disease, the emphasis is on administering anti-infective medications during the acute phase of the illness, while managing complications during the determinate stage. Two antiparasitic drugs, benznidazole and nifurtimox, are utilized for Chagas disease treatment. These medications demonstrate their highest efficacy during the acute phase of the disease, achieving parasitological cure rates ranging from 60% to 80%.

For patients with severe systolic dysfunction (left ventricular ejection fraction), cardiac resynchronization therapy may be an option. If these patients do not respond to maximum medical treatment for heart failure, the consideration of a left ventricular assist device and, eventually, cardiac transplantation may be warranted. Sudden cardiac death is the primary cause of mortality in these patients. The use of an implantable cardioverter-defibrillator has been employed to avert sudden cardiac death in individuals with Chagas cardiomyopathy.

There is evidence indicating that amiodarone can improve survival rates in individuals at high risk of arrhythmic death. As a result, amiodarone is recommended as the preferred treatment for individuals with sustained ventricular tachycardia, as well as for those with non-sustained ventricular tachycardia and myocardial dysfunction. Additionally, the combination of implantable cardioverter-defibrillator therapy with amiodarone has demonstrated superiority over amiodarone alone for the secondary prevention of sudden death in patients with Chagas cardiomyopathy. Patients with high degree atrioventricular block or symptomatic bradycardia should be treated with permanent cardiac pacing.

3.3 MISCARRIAGE

Toxoplasma gondii, an intracellular protozoan, can infect a wide range of warm-blooded species, encompassing humans and livestock alike. While felids serve as the definitive hosts for *T. gondii*, other warm-blooded animals can act as intermediate hosts. In the past decade, there has been a documented reduction in the incidence of *T. gondii* infection among human populations. Infection with *T. gondii* during pregnancy can lead to miscarriage, fetal demise, and ocular or cerebral abnormalities in medical terminology. Sheep demonstrate significant susceptibility to *T. gondii* infection. Studies suggest that the meat, internal organs, blood, and milk of sheep or goats experiencing acute toxoplasmosis have the potential to act as modes of transmitting the parasite to both animals and humans.

The prevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection escalates with age, and the infection rate varies significantly among countries and regions due to differences in dietary habits, healthcare standards, and socioeconomic status. Enhanced hygiene practices, advancements in agricultural systems, and improved socioeconomic conditions have led to a reduction in infection rates in many developed countries.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

- Seizures
- Enlarged liver or spleen
- Jaundice (yellowing of skin and eyes)
- Serious eye infections

Other manifestations, such as encephalitis, myocarditis, hepatitis, and pneumonia, are rare but can complicate acute toxoplasmosis. In rare cases, ocular infection with visual loss can occur.

In patients with AIDS, toxoplasmic encephalitis is the most common cause of intracerebral mass lesions and is thought to usually be caused by reactivation of chronic infection [25-27]

LIFE CYCLE TOXOPLASMA GONDII

Fig 8: Life cycle of *Toxoplasma gondii*

SOURCE: Centre For Disease Control And Prevention.

During a span of 1–3 weeks, oocysts are usually shed, and they can be shed in significant amounts. The process of sporulation, during which oocysts become infectious, takes 1–5 days in the environment. In their natural habitat, intermediate hosts like birds and rodents become infected by consuming soil, water, or plant material that has been contaminated with oocysts.

Shortly after ingestion, oocysts undergo a transformation into tachyzoites. These tachyzoites then localize in neural and muscle tissue, where they develop into tissue cyst bradyzoites.

After consuming intermediate hosts that contain cysts of tissue, cats develop the disease.

The ingestion of sporulated oocysts can also cause cats to be infected directly. After ingestion of sporulated oocysts in the environment, animals bred for human consumption and wild game may also be infected with tissue cysts.

Infection to humans by various routes

Consuming undercooked meat of animals harbouring tissue cysts

Consuming food or water contaminated with cat feces or by contaminated environmental samples.

Blood transfusion or organ transplantation

Trans placentally from mother to foetus

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

During its life cycle, *T. gondii* has three stages in development. Oocysts are caused by the sexual reproduction phase, which occurs in the small intestine of a felid that has recently eaten tissue cysts, which are typically found in raw meat. For about two weeks after the initial infection, oocysts form in a cat and occupy infectious sporozoites.

Following deposition by the cat, these oocysts become infectious within a period ranging from one to five days. Tachyzoites are rapidly dividing products that occur in macrophages after invasion of the host intestinal wall by either sporozoites originating from oocysts or bradyzoites originating from tissue cysts. There are three primary modes of *Toxoplasma gondii* (*T. gondii*) infection in humans.

- Firstly, ingestion of tissue cysts present in contaminated, not well-cooked meat can lead to infection. Bradyzoites, the dormant form of the parasite, can be present in varying percentages in different types of meat such as **beef (up to 8%), pork (up to 20%), and lamb (up to 20%)**. It effectively eliminates bradyzoites and mitigates the risk of this mode of transmission by cooking meat to an internal temperature of 67 C or freezing it at a temperature of less than 12 °C.
- Secondly, ingestion of infective oocysts through fecal-oral contact can result in infection as sporozoites are released, subsequently invading the intestinal wall.
- Thirdly, although rare, infection can occur through blood transfusions if blood from an infected individual containing circulating tachyzoites is transfused into a nonimmune recipient.[28]

Transplacental transmission of tachyzoites to the fetus is a cause of Congenital Toxoplasmosis. In individuals with a normally functioning immune system, this mode of infection occurs exclusively when a pregnant woman acquires a primary infection. Once an adequate immune response has been achieved, those previously exposed to the parasite are rarely infected again. The risk of congenital toxoplasmosis stemming from maternal primary infection escalates throughout pregnancy, from 0% in the initial trimester to 9%, and up to 35% to 59% in the final trimester. Fortunately, the later in gestation that congenital infection occurs, the milder its impact on fetal health [29]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

There are strong indications of previous infections with *T. gondii* all over the world. In the United States, the overall seroprevalence adjusted for age is 22.5%, and among women of childbearing age (15 to 44 years), it stands at 15%. Annually, there are approximately 225,000 cases of *T. gondii* infection leading to 5000 hospitalizations and 750 fatalities, positioning *T. gondii* as the third most prevalent cause of fatal foodborne illness in the country. Despite the common occurrence of prior infection, congenital toxoplasmosis is relatively rare in the United States, with an estimated annual occurrence of **400 to 4000** cases.[30]

DIAGNOSIS

Serological tests and PCR are used in an attempt to diagnose toxoplasmosis in pregnant women. Transmission of the parasite to the fetus frequently occurs in pregnant women who have no history of illness during gestation or exposure to undercooked meat or cats.

SEROLOGICAL TESTS

The identification and measurement of *T. gondii* antibodies in serum serve as diagnostic tools to ascertain whether a pregnant woman has encountered the infection and to distinguish between recent and past infections. In cases where serological tests indicate a recent infection, further investigations are undertaken to determine if the infection likely occurred during pregnancy or shortly before conception. In such instances, there is a potential risk to the fetus.

In serological diagnosis, various types of antibodies including IgG, IgM, IgA, and IgE, as well as IgG avidity and differential agglutination (AC/HS) tests, are utilized to differentiate between the acute and chronic phases of the infection. However, these tests are usually only performed in specialized reference laboratories, aside from measuring IgG and IgM antibodies.

First, clinical, nonreference laboratories should test for both IgG and IgM antibodies serologically. Testing early in pregnancy can usually determine whether an infection has occurred or not by looking for both IgG and IgM antibodies. If an infection was acquired long ago, it can be determined by looking for positive IgG and negative IgM antibody test results. The best way to interpret serological test results appropriately is to provide experienced consultants with sufficient clinical information, such as gestational age, the reason for the test, and the existence of abnormal clinical or laboratory findings in the mother or the fetus.

1. In a commercial or non-reference laboratory

2. Because only approximately 10% of pregnant women in the US are seropositive, this is useful for initial screening.

2. In the PAMF-TS reference laboratory

Especially helpful for expectant mothers whose IgM test results are unclear or positive

3. PCR in amniotic fluid

For pregnant women with suspected or confirmed toxoplasmosis during pregnancy, it should be done at 18 weeks of gestation, or as soon as practical after; the 35-multicopy B1 gene is typically used as the target.

There has been no research on the sensitivity and specificity of PCR testing for amniotic fluid obtained before 18 weeks of gestation. Furthermore, carrying out this procedure early in pregnancy increases the risk to the fetus and may only provide limited diagnostic value specificity and positive predictive value, both of which were found to be 100% positive results indicating fetus infection.

4. Ultrasound

For women who have been diagnosed or suspected of having an acute infection during or shortly before pregnancy, ultrasound is advised. Fetal anomalies such as hydrocephalus, hepatic or brain calcifications, splenomegaly, and ascites may be detected by ultrasound. The clinical result of congenitally infected children who received spiramycin during

gestation, whose mothers had contracted the infection during the first trimester of pregnancy, and whose fetal ultrasound findings were normal, was recently reported. Even though it was anticipated that these children would suffer serious harm

5. Histopathological examination and endeavors to separate the parasite

To examine possible vertical transmission of the parasite, placental, or fetal tissues from pregnant women suspected of developing an acute infection during gestation may occasionally be made available. Wright-Giemsa stain can be used to visualize *T. gondii* cysts in these tissues, but immune peroxidase staining with antibodies specific to *T. gondii* is more sensitive. It is possible to isolate the parasite by inoculating tissues into mice or tissue cultures.[31]

THE TREATMENT STRATEGY FOR PATIENTS WHO HAVE BEEN DIAGNOSED OR ARE SUSPECTED OF HAVING CONTRACTED T. GONDII DURING PREGNANCY.

To stop the parasite from spreading vertically, many clinicians in the US and Europe advise starting spiramycin treatment for the mother as soon as serological test results confirm recent infection and the possible risk of fetal transmission during the first 18 weeks of gestation or around conception.

Subsequently, if fetal infection is verified through a positive PCR result from amniotic fluid at or after **18 weeks** of gestation, **administration of pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine, and folinic acid** is recommended. Should the patient already be undergoing spiramycin therapy, the protocol advises transitioning to this combination treatment. Certain European medical institutions implement this transition as early as weeks 14 to 16.

SPIRAMYCIN

DOSAGE-1 g (3 million U) every 8 h (for a total of 3 g or 9 million U per day)

The macrolide antibiotic spiramycin has been documented to lower the rate of vertical transmission, but rigorous prospective studies validating this effect are lacking. Notably, its protective efficacy appears more pronounced in women acquiring the infection during the initial trimester of pregnancy. Investigations employing historical controls have shown a reduction of approximately **60%** in the occurrence of congenital infection. However, spiramycin's limited placental crossing ability renders it unreliable for directly treating fetal infection.

There is no evidence that spiramycin is known to have teratogenic effects. Consequently, it is administered throughout the remainder of pregnancy, even if amniotic fluid PCR results are negative. This precaution is taken due to the theoretical risk of fetal infection occurring later in gestation from a previously infected placenta. In pregnant individuals with a high likelihood of fetal infection or in cases where fetal infection has been confirmed, the treatment protocol typically involves transitioning from spiramycin to pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine, and folinic acid after the 18th week of gestation. In certain medical facilities, this transition may occur earlier, such as between 14 and 16 weeks of gestation.

PYRIMETHAMINE, SULFADIAZINE, AND FOLINIC ACID

DOSAGE:

50 mg of **pyrimethamine** every 12 hours for two days, then 50 mg every day after that **Sulfadiazine** 75 mg/kg as starting dose, then 50 mg/kg every 12 hours (maximum, 4 g/day) 10–20 mg of **folinic acid** (leucovorin) per day if pyrimethamine therapy is being completed, and for one week thereafter. For pregnant women who contract the infection after 18 weeks of pregnancy, as well as those whose fetal infection has been confirmed (i.e., by a positive result of amniotic fluid PCR) or is highly suspected (e.g., because of fetal abnormalities consistent with congenital toxoplasmosis detected by ultrasound examination), the combination of pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine, and folinic acid is recommended initially.

This drug regimen is employed to treat fetal infection and, in certain cases, aims to prevent transmission. This is particularly relevant for pregnant women who are unable to undergo amniocentesis for PCR testing and who contracted the infection after 18 weeks of gestation.

Since pyrimethamine may cause teratogenic effects, it is not advised to be used during the first trimester of pregnancy. The medication causes a dose-related, reversible, and typically gradual depression of the bone marrow. Complete blood cell counts should be routinely checked in all patients receiving pyrimethamine.

The drug's hematological toxicities are reduced and prevented by folinic acid, not folic acid. [32-34]

APPROACH FOR OTHERWISE IMMUNOCOMPETENT PATIENTS: INFECTION WITH T. GONDII IS MOSTLY ADVANCED AFTER ≥ 6 MONTHS OF GESTATION

The incidence of congenital toxoplasmosis in offspring is extremely rare, almost zero, in cases where women are confirmed to have had toxoplasmosis before conception or exhibit serological evidence of prior infection.

Therefore, unless the mother's immune system is compromised, the administration of spiramycin or the combination therapy of pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine, and folinic acid along with a prenatal diagnosis of fetal infection is not advised.

APPROACH FOR PREGNANT WOMEN WHO ARE SUSPECTED OR CONFIRMED TO HAVE TOXOPLASMOSIS ACQUIRED DURING GESTATION [35]

3.4 CLONORCHIASIS

Clonorchiasis, also known as Chinese liver fluke disease is a common food-borne parasitic infection mainly caused by *Clonorchis sinensis* (*C. sinensis*), which lives in the human intrahepatic bile duct. It was first reported in 1875 by McConnell, who found a new species of liver fluke in the bile ducts during autopsy. Later identification identified *C. sinensis* as the pathogenic agent. The infection is contracted by eating raw or undercooked freshwater fish contaminated with *C. sinensis*, therefore a food-borne zoonotic transmission. Clonorchiasis can cause a wide range of hepatobiliary disorders, from asymptomatic colonization to severe hepatic conditions like cholangitis or portal hypertension.

Most cases of clonorchiasis are found in endemic regions of eastern Asia, such as China, Japan, the Korean Peninsula, etc. With an estimated 13 million people infected with clonorchiasis, China has the highest percentage.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

It includes,

Most infected people don't exhibit any symptoms. Constipation, diarrhea, indigestion, and abdominal pain are possible symptoms in mild cases. The majority of symptoms and indicators are connected to bile duct inflammation and sporadic obstruction. Diarrhea, nausea, and abdominal pain can happen in severe cases.

In mild cases, manifestations include mild abdominal symptoms. Patients with high worm burdens often have other nonspecific symptoms such as abdominal pain (particularly in the right upper abdominal quadrant) and various somatic symptoms (e.g. headache, dizziness)

In cases of prolonged infection, symptoms tend to intensify, often accompanied by hepatomegaly and malnutrition.

Additionally, less frequently observed but notable complications may include biliary disorders such as cholangitis, cholelithiasis, cholecystitis, and cholangiocarcinoma, as well as pancreatitis and liver abscess formation. [36]

LIFE CYCLE OF CLONORCHIS SINENSIS

Asian liver disease is primarily caused by the trematode *Clonorchis sinensis*, also known as the Chinese or oriental liver fluke. It is a significant foodborne pathogen. It seems that this is the only species in the genus that can infect humans.

More than one hundred different species of freshwater fish and numerous species of snails serve as intermediate hosts for *C. sinensis*. Most of these fish species are members of the Cyprinidae family, which includes minnows and carp. Moreover, *C. sinensis* metacercariae has been detected in a few species of shrimp in some Chinese regions, though at much lower frequencies and metacercarial loads than in cyprinid fish. In addition to humans, other definitive hosts include swine, mustelids, domestic dogs and cats, and other piscivorous mammals.

Fig 9: Life cycle of *Clonorchis sinensis*

SOURCE: Centre For Disease Control And Prevention

Clonorchis sinensis eggs are discharged in the biliary ducts and the stool in an embryonated state.

1. A suitable intermediate host snail consumes the eggs.

Miracidia are released by eggs and go through several stages of development, including sporocysts, rediae, and cercariae.

Following their release from the snail, the cercariae swim freely for a brief while before coming into contact with freshwater fish flesh and penetrating it to become metacercariae.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

C. sinensis causes periductal fibroplasia early in the infection (say, 7 days after infection), which later transforms into liver parenchyma.

The advancement of clonorchiasis differs from that of hepatic fibrosis induced by viral hepatitis or alcohol consumption. It is believed that distinct molecular pathways underlie these diseases. Excretory-secretory products (ESPs) from *C. sinensis* are implicated in the progression of clonorchiasis. Some of the components of ESP, such as Fe heavy chain protein (CsFHC), fructose-1, 6-bisphosphatase (CsFBPase), lysophospholipase (CslysoPLA), and secretory phospholipase A(2) (CsPLA2), have been shown to directly stimulate human hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) and other key cells involved in liver fibrosis, thereby encouraging the production of collagen.

Following infection, the TGF- β /Smad signaling pathway may become active, potentially leading to the production of type I collagen and fibroplasia. Hepatocyte hydropic degeneration may be brought on by *C. sinensis* infection via the Fas/FasL pathway. ESPs and their constituents, such as Csseverin, may inhibit the apoptosis of malignant or abnormal cells (such as PLC, a hepatocarcinoma cell line, or HuCCT1, a CCA cell line), potentially leading to the formation of tumors.

Furthermore, it has been established that immune responses, particularly inflammation, play a significant role in the pathogenesis of fibrosis and carcinoma. Nam et al. demonstrated that free radicals, enzymatically triggered by *C. sinensis* ESPs, induce NF- κ B-mediated inflammation in HuCCT1 cells.

Prolonged inflammation has the potential to cause DNA damage, leading to cellular malignant transformation. Both crude antigens of *C. sinensis* and ESP components, such as CsRNASET2, have been shown to substantially increase Th2-associated cytokines including IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, IL-10, and TGF- β in *C. sinensis*-infected mice, primarily through their impact on dendritic cells.

Moreover, levels of IL-33/ST2, a potent inducer of bile duct proliferation and fibrosis, were markedly elevated in patients infected with *C. sinensis*. [37]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Clonorchis sinensis is a carcinogenic liver fluke that causes clonorchiasis in humans. Clonorchiasis is prevalent in East Asian countries, and approximately 15–20 million individuals are estimated to be infected with this fluke globally. A recent survey has shown that in *C. sinensis* infection rate in Korea, *C. sinensis* infections remain endemic in 5 major river basins (Han-gang, Geum-gang, Seomjin-gang, Yeongsan-gang, and Nakdong-gang; gang means river) with a high incidence of cholangiocarcinoma

DIAGNOSIS

Adult *C. sinensis* worms can reside within the bile ducts for extended periods, typically ranging from 20 to 25 years. During the early stages of infection, clinical manifestations are often absent, leading to frequent instances of undiagnosed cases. clonorchiasis is usually misdiagnosed due to its nonspecific symptoms, such as fatigue, inappetence, nausea, bellyache, jaundice, and hepatosplenomegaly. People who live in or have come from epidemic areas, have consumed raw or undercooked freshwater fish, and appear with the above symptoms should be considered suspects for clonorchiasis.

1. STOOL EXAMINATION

Eggs found in stool can confirm *C. sinensis* infection. Stool examination is inexpensive and does not require the use of sophisticated equipment.

2. COMMON METHODS

- Direct fecal smear, the Kato-Katz (KK) method
- The formalin-ether concentration technique (FECT)

Hong et al. reported that although FECT was more sensitive than the KK method for diagnosing very light infection cases, the KK method was more reliable for diagnosing clonorchiasis. Qian et al. proposed that the KK method was more reliable than FECT for the diagnosis and drug efficacy evaluation of clonorchiasis.

However, the eggs of *C. sinensis* are easily confused with the eggs of other flukes (e.g., Opisthorchiidae, Lecithodendriidae, or Heterophyidae).

2. SEROLOGICAL METHODS

Serological techniques are valuable in diagnosing clonorchiasis. In serum samples, the presence of specific antibodies or antigens of *C. sinensis* can be detected. Generally, detection of specific antibodies is more common due to the limited amount of antigen and sensitivity constraints. However, Nie et al. demonstrated that an IgY (egg yolk immunoglobulin)-based immunomagnetic bead enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) system (IgY-IMB-ELISA) is a sensitive and specific method for detecting circulating antigens in human clonorchiasis. Furthermore, a significant correlation has been established between ELISA optical density and egg counts.

Crude extracts from *C. sinensis* are often deemed sufficiently sensitive for serodiagnosis of clonorchiasis; however, they may exhibit cross-reactivity with other trematodes. To address this limitation, efforts have focused on utilizing purified recombinant proteins derived from the tegument or excretory/secretory proteins (ESPs) of the worm. Notable candidates include the 21.1-kDa tegumental protein, cathepsin L proteinase, cysteine protease, and a fragment of para myosin (CsPmyC-2), which have been extensively evaluated for their diagnostic potential. Among diagnostic assays, the IgG4-ABC (avidin-biotin complex)-ELISA stands out as more sensitive and specific compared to IgG-ELISA or IgG4-ELISA, as it targets specific IgG4 antibodies against *C. sinensis*.

PCR METHODS

DNA-based techniques can also be used for diagnosis. Sensitive and specific target genes, such as internal transcribed spacers (ITS-1 or ITS-2) of nuclear ribosomal DNA (rDNA), *cox1*, *Rn1*, and *nad2*, have been documented. Different PCR techniques have been used, including real-time PCR, multiplex PCR, PCR-RFLP, and FRET PCR. However, because PCR requires special equipment, these techniques are not appropriate for use in less developed areas.

IMAGING METHODS

Imaging modalities including CT, MRI, THI, ultrasound, and tissue harmonic imaging (THI) are used to assess the progression of disease and offer useful supplementary diagnostic capabilities. However, these methods show a lack of sensitivity and specificity, and they could be difficult for staff members with little experience. Moreover, the process of implementing them may be highly expensive.

TREATMENT

1. PRAZIQUANTEL

Praziquantel (PZQ) is an effective treatment for clonorchiasis, provided that the disease is correctly diagnosed and treated at an early stage. As per recommendations from the World Health Organization (WHO), Treatments consisting of three daily doses of 25 mg/kg given for two days in a row have shown cure rates ranging from 93.9% to 100%.

Between 2001 and 2004, a clonorchiasis control program was implemented in endemic regions of China by a study conducted by Choi et al. They found that administering Praziquantel (PZQ) in large doses or as a targeted treatment every six to twelve months was quite successful. This approach resulted in low prevalence and re-infection rates, along with a high egg reduction rate, particularly in heavily endemic areas, and to a lesser extent in moderately endemic areas.

2. TRIBENDIMIDINE

Tribendimidine has shown great efficacy in treating *C. sinensis* in rats and hamsters as well as in vitro. Tribendimidine has been shown in two recent comparative clinical studies to be just as effective as PZQ in treating *C. sinensis* infections, and in certain dosage regimens, even more so. Other drugs such as artemether, artesunate, OZ78, and mebendazole have also been evaluated for treating *C. sinensis* infection in animal models.

MEBENDAZOLE

Administer 400 milligrams orally as a single dose. It is used for Co-infection with other helminths.[38]

PREVENTION AND CONTROL STRATEGY

- The typical approach to preventing and controlling clonorchiasis entails combining two or more strategies, such as environmental reconstruction, health promotion, chemotherapy, and health education.
- Health education encompasses the dissemination of informative content through television programming, radio broadcasts, VCDs, billboard advertisements, and mural paintings, as well as the giving out of health-related leaflets and teaching residents and students about particular diseases. When it comes to environmental reconstitution, removing pigsties and toilets from fishpond areas is beneficial. Reconstructive efforts in health education and promotion initiatives can augment understanding of *C. sinensis* infection and the imperative to abstain from consuming raw or inadequately cooked freshwater fish. This endeavor typically facilitates chemotherapy adherence and contributes to environmental remediation.
- PZQ-based mass chemotherapy has been implemented in numerous endemic regions and exhibits the potential for effectively managing clonorchiasis.
- Given the possible tolerance and adverse reactions associated with PZQ, there is a suggested need for the advancement and endorsement of anthelmintic medications that are both safe and efficacious.
- Eliminating the consumption of raw freshwater fish or shrimp appears to be the most effective method to prevent infection by *C. sinensis* and other fish-borne zoonotic trematodes. But people living in endemic areas find it difficult to change

their eating habits, especially when it comes to eating raw fish and shrimp, and they often get the chance to eat food that contains raw fish. As a result, more effort needs to be put into guaranteeing the security of freshwater fish. Therefore, more attention should be paid to the safety of freshwater fish. The infection rates and distribution of freshwater fish and snails should be investigated in endemic areas, and infected ponds should be placed under surveillance. Additionally, metacercaria-tainted fish should be barred from markets

- *C. sinensis* metacercariae in freshwater fish are examined by direct compression or artificial digestion, followed by microscopic detection. Because *C. sinensis* is easily confused with other parasites (such as Opisthorchiidae, Heterophyidae, and Lecithodendriidae), this method is labor-intensive and time-consuming. At this stage. Using non-polluted water for the culture of fish combined with the use of a fish vaccine against *C. sinensis* infection will be helpful to reduce *C. sinensis* infections and aid in the supervision of the safety of freshwater fish.

The approaches put forth by the World Health Organization (WHO), the National Health and Family Planning Commission (NHFPC) of the People's Republic of China, and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) of the United States are outlined below.

CDC	Eat only properly cooked freshwater fish (internal temperature > 63 °C) or freeze it (≤ -20 °C for 7 days; ≤ -35 °C for 15 hours). Avoid eating raw or undercooked freshwater fish.
WHO	Suggesting food safety procedures and veterinary public health initiatives to lower the risk of infection, as well as enhancing the efficacy and safety of anthelmintic medications to reduce morbidity
NHFPC	Enhancing the township or village's coverage of anthelmintic medication standards and sanitary restrooms; raising awareness of health behaviors and parasite prevention and control; and raising the proportion of qualified medical personnel

3.5 CYSTIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS (CE)

Since human CE has been reported on every continent save Antarctica, it is a significant global public health concern. The larval stage of *Echinococcus granulosus*, a member of the Taeniidae family, is the etiological agent of CE. Its host range, morphology, genetic diversity, pathogenicity, developing rate, antigenicity, and infectivity to humans are highly variable. The first stage of the *Echinococcus* species' parasite life cycle consists of a definitive host, such as dogs, which may harbor the adult worm in the intestine and potentially discharge eggs into the surrounding environment through excrement. The next stage is an intermediate host, which is usually represented by ruminants and only atypically by humans because human infection is an epidemiological phenomenon rather than a lifecycle maintainer.[39]

Hydatidosis, also known as hydatid disease, or human echinococcosis, is brought on by the larval stages of cestodes, or tapeworms, belonging to the genus *Echinococcus*. The most common type of echinococcosis is caused by *Echinococcus granulosus* (*sensu lato*). *E. multilocularis* is another species that is more prevalent and causes alveolar echinococcosis. "Neotropical echinococcosis" is linked to two solely New World species: *E. vogeli* and *E. oligarthrus*. *E. vogeli* causes a polycystic form, while *E. oligarchus* cause the incredibly rare unicystic form.

Different host ranges, distribution patterns, and morphological characteristics have been found for many genotypes of *E. granulosus*; in contemporary literature, these genotypes are frequently classified as distinct species. The "classical" *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1–G3), *E. outleaps* (G5), and the *E. canadensis* group (usually regarded as G6, G7, G8, and G10) are among the known zoonotic genotypes within the *E. granulosus sensu lato* complex. There is currently no agreement on proper nomenclature despite years of research on the epidemiology and diversity of these genotypes.

In humans, *Echinococcus granulosus* cysts typically manifest in organs such as the liver or lungs, leading to signs of disease attributable to hepatic or pulmonary dysfunction. Infrequently, cysts may arise in bones, precipitating spontaneous fractures, or in the brain, resulting in neurological manifestations. *Echinococcus multilocularis* cysts or lesions predominantly affect the liver, exhibiting gradual growth accompanied by significant hepatic pathology and considerable mortality risk if left untreated. Additionally, there's a chance of cyst rupture, triggering severe allergic reactions in affected individuals.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

- About 50% of patients who undergo medical treatment for infection do so within a few years of contracting the parasite for the first time. The disease may take years to manifest symptoms of incubation before hydatid cysts enlarge to the point where they cause symptoms.
The symptoms of stomach pain, nausea, and vomiting are often observed when hydatids develop in the liver. Constant coughing, chest pain, and dyspnea are clinical signs of lung involvement.

- The location of the hydatid cysts and the force exerted on the surrounding tissues determine whether or not there are any more signs.
A few non-specific symptoms are weakness, anorexia, and weight loss.

Fig 10: Life cycle of *Cystic echinococcus*

SOURCE: Centre For Disease Control And Prevention

LIFE CYCLE OF CYSTIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS

It dwells in the final host's small intestine. Eggs are released by gravid proglottids.

They are instantly contagious and are transferred through faeces. Six-hooked oncospheres are released from eggs in the small intestine following ingestion by an appropriate intermediate host.

It enters the body through the intestinal wall and move into the liver and lungs among other organs via the circulatory system. The oncosphere transforms into a thick-walled hydatid cyst in these organs.

Fig 11: Microscopical Examination of *Echinococcus granulosus*,

EPIDEMIOLOGY

With a global distribution, cystic echinococcosis poses a serious threat to public health in some areas. In regions like the Mediterranean, central Asia, western China, East Africa, Peru, Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, and southern Brazil, it is thought to be endemic.

Around the world, 88% of human cases of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* are caused by the G1 genotype. It is found all over the world and is thought to spread via sheep, which serves as an intermediary host. Globally, *E. canadensis* G6 and G7 cause 3.7% and 7.3% of infections, respectively.

In areas where echinococcosis is endemic, human incidence rates can exceed 50 cases per 100,000 person-years, and prevalence rates can be as high as 5% to 10% in places like China, Peru, Argentina, and East Africa. A minimum of one million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) are lost each year due to echinococcosis, and the disease costs \$3 billion in treatment and livestock losses.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Upon ingestion of tapeworm eggs by humans, the oncosphere larva emerges from the egg and proceeds to invade the lamina propria of the intestinal wall.

Subsequently, it undergoes passive transportation via either the bloodstream or lymphatic vessels to various internal organs such as the liver, lungs, or other visceral structures, where it matures into hydatid cysts, known as meta cestode larvae.

These cysts comprise a deep germinal layer and an outer laminated layer encased within a fibrous capsule formed by host tissue. Within the cyst, smaller daughter cysts develop from the inner cellular layer.

In human hosts, cysts exhibit slow growth and can attain substantial volumes, potentially reaching several liters, and harboring numerous protoscolices.

Over time, the development of septations and daughter cysts leads to the disruption of the typical unilocular pattern observed in echinococcal cysts.[40]

DIAGNOSIS

The primary method for diagnosing cystic echinococcosis is imaging. A standardized classification of ultrasound images was published in 2003 by the World Health Organization Informal Working Group on Echinococcosis (WHO-IWGE). This classification was based on the initial one created in 1981 by H. A. Gharbi, W. Hassine, M. W. Brauner, and K. Dupuch.

The cystic lesion (CL) stage encompasses unilocular cystic lesions observed on ultrasound, lacking pathognomonic features, necessitating further investigation to confirm their parasitic nature. Recently, the CE3 subgroup, characterized by transitional cysts, has been subdivided into **two samples, CE3a (showing a detached endocyst) and CE3b (mainly solid with daughter vesicles), which differ in their metabolic profiles and how they react to non-surgical treatments.**

Unlike CE3b cysts, which are always active, CE3a cysts are truly transitional cysts because they can be either inactive or active. This classification was created based on an analysis of liver cysts caused by cystic echinococcosis; however, it can also be used in several other situations to manage and monitor cysts that are located elsewhere.

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

When it comes to identifying the structural characteristics that define a cyst's stage, MRI performs better than CT scans.

A vital role is played by MRI imaging combined with MR cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) in the preoperative evaluation of complications like cysto-biliary fistulas. Despite being non-invasive, it shows similar effectiveness to endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) in identifying biliary obstruction. Cysto-biliary fistulas usually appear after the endocyst ruptures, especially in stages CE2 and CE3b. In these stages, MRCP shows a 75% sensitivity and a 95% specificity in identifying cysto-biliary fistulas.

CLINICAL LABORATORY ANALYSIS

In patients with cystic echinococcosis, clinical laboratory analysis, including chemistry and hematology testing, is nonspecific.

Those with biliary blockage may have elevated gamma-glutamyl transferase, transaminases, and bilirubin levels. When cyst rupture or leakage into the biliary tree transpires, eosinophilia—a marker that is normally absent in intact cysts—as well as significant elevations in gamma-glutamyl transferase and alkaline phosphatase may be observed.

IMMUNODIAGNOSTICS

Immunodiagnosics' limitations in terms of sensitivity and specificity make them an adjunct in diagnosis. Serology, however, might help in confirming or supporting a cystic echinococcosis diagnosis. Recommendations from the World Health Organization and the World Organization for Animal Health call for sequential testing using a screening and confirmatory test model.

The most widely used primary screening techniques are enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA), immunofluorescence antibody tests (IFAT), latex agglutination (LAT), indirect hemagglutination antibody tests (IHAT), and immunoelectrophoresis (IEP).

These techniques, particularly in patients with other helminthic infections, have variable sensitivity and relatively low specificity. Antigen material from animal liver hydatid cysts, whether crude or refined, is used in many assays and is probably a major source of variation in test performance.

Studies on the application of recombinant antigens for serodiagnosis have been carried out, and the results indicate that these antigens have a higher sensitivity when used in place of native antigens or their purified subunits. To further investigate this strategy, though, more research is necessary.

MICROSCOPICAL EXAMINATION

In cases where diagnostic aspiration is deemed necessary, although infrequently indicated, a microscopic examination of cyst fluid can be conducted to verify the presence of *Echinococcus* spp. This confirmation is typically achieved by noticing protoscolices and/or free hooklets. A straightforward and often sufficient method for this diagnosis is the wet unstained mount procedure. Furthermore, whether hooklets are isolated or attached to protoscolices, various staining techniques such as modified Baxby stain, Wheatley trichrome or Ryan trichrome blue stain, Ziehl-Neelsen stain, and Baxby stain can enhance their visibility. Identifying cyst material can also be done with histologic tissue sections. These sections usually display an acellular laminated layer and a thin cellular germinal layer containing protoscolices and brood capsules in mature echinococcal cysts.

TREATMENT

The management of cystic echinococcosis is complex and is beyond the scope of this review. The WHO-IWGE published an "Expert Consensus for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis in Humans" in 2010.

Surgery has been considered the gold standard, but alternatives exist for selected patients and are now considered the first management option.

The decision-making process regarding treatment options relies heavily on several factors, including the proficiency of the healthcare team, resource availability, the cyst's size, location, and stage; additionally, whether any symptoms or complications are present. Notably, there is no conclusive test to confirm a cure, so long-term imaging follow-up is required to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment, especially in light of the possibility that serology results may remain positive for a long time even after successful treatment. Whenever feasible, patients should undergo evaluation at specialized referral centers.

Despite benzimidazoles serving as the primary medical treatment since the late 1980s, several unresolved issues persist, including concerns regarding the optimal period of therapy. Numerous compounds have been experimentally tested without success rate. Despite evidence suggesting potential synergy between benzimidazoles and other agents like metformin in laboratory settings, there remains a significant demand for investment in the growth of novel chemotherapeutic agents.[41-42]

PREVENTION AND CONTROL

The prevention of the disease depends on the interruption of the life cycle of *E. granulosus*. For example, regular screening and treatment of infected dogs have been successful in eradicating the disease in areas of endemicity such as New Zealand • Control stray dog populations.

- Restrict home slaughter of sheep and other livestock.
- Do not consume any food or water that may have been contaminated by fecal matter from dogs.
- Wash your hands with soap and warm water after handling dogs, and before handling food.
- Teach children the importance of washing hands to prevent infection. Vaccination of sheep with an *E. granulosus* recombinant antigen (EG95) offers encouraging prospects for prevention and control. The vaccine is currently being produced commercially and is registered in China and Argenti [43-44]

4. DISCUSSION

This study summarizes food-borne disease outbreaks for the first time and provides control and preventive measures for the diseases listed above to improve public health and lower the death rate. Despite growing awareness of food safety, food-borne disease incidences have reached an epidemic level worldwide, with 600 million cases of illness. In India, a surveillance program has been implemented to gather information about outbreaks that may be used to design preventive actions.

5. CONCLUSION

The main foodborne parasites that are spread by pork, freshwater fish, freshwater crustaceans, etc., were covered in this article. Food safety precautions are crucial in the fight against these parasites. Various authorities in various nations must prevent human exposure to these foodborne illnesses, or in certain nations, it may not be the duty of any authority at all. It is challenging to identify parasites in animals because the afflicted animals may not exhibit any symptoms of the disease and because there are no economic or productivity losses as a result of the illness. *Taenia solium*, *Trichinella* spp., and *Toxoplasma gondii* are noted as parasitic diseases spread by pork. The number and location of these diseases are among the factors that determine their severity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bintsis T, Department of International Trade, TEI of West Macedonia, Kastoria, Greece. Foodborne pathogens. *AIMS Microbiology*. 2017;3(3):529–63.
- [2] Parasites in food – An invisible thread, Food and agricultural organizations of the United Nations,2021;2-5.
- [3] Robertson LJ. Parasites in Food: From a Neglected Position to an Emerging Issue. In: *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research* [Internet]. Elsevier; 2018 [cited 2024 Mar 9]. p. 71–
- [4] Parasites in food – An invisible thread, Food and agricultural organizations of the United Nations,2021;2-5.
- [5] Bisht A, Kamble MP, Choudhary P, Chaturvedi K, Kohli G, Juneja VK, et al. A surveillance of foodborne disease outbreaks in India: 2009–2018. *Food Control*. 2021 Mar;121:107630.
- [6] Health education in food safety. Geneva, World Health Organization, 1988 (unpublished document WHO/EHE/FOS/88.7).
- [7] Lalitha, M.K., Walter, N.M., Jesudason, M. and Mathan, V.I. An abstract of Gastroenteritis due to *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* in Vellore. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 1983;78: 611-
- [8] Thekdi, R.J., Lakhani, A.G., Rale, V.B., and Panre, M.V. An outbreak of food poisoning suspected to be caused by *vibrio fluvialis*. *Journal of Diarrheal Diseases Research*. 1990; 8 (4):163-5.
- [9] García HH, Gonzalez AE, Evans CA, Gilman RH. *Taenia solium* cysticercosis. *The Lancet*. 2003 Aug;362(9383):547–56.
- [10] <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/taeniasis-cysticercosis>
- [11] James L. Smith, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Agriculture Research Service, Eastern Regional Research Center, *Taenia solium* Neurocysticercosis, *Journal of Food Protection*, Vol. 57, No.9, Pages 831-844.
- [12] Garcia HH, Nash TE, Del Brutto OH. Clinical symptoms, diagnosis, and treatment of neurocysticercosis. *Lancet Neurol*. 2014 Dec;13(12):1202–15.
- [13] Saraiva RM, Mediano MFF, Mendes FS, Sperandio da Silva GM, Veloso HH, Sangenis LHC, et al. Chagas heart disease: An overview of diagnosis, manifestations, treatment, and care. *World J Cardiol*. 2021 Dec 26;13(12):654–75.
- [14] Kuschnir E, Sgammini H, Castro R, Evequoz C, Ledesma R, Brunetto J. [Evaluation of cardiac function by radioisotopic angiography, in patients with chronic Chagas cardiopathy]. *Arq Bras Cardiol* 1985; 45: 249-256.
- [15] Andrade JP, Marin-Neto JA, Paola AA, Vilas-Boas F, Oliveira GM, Bacal F, Bocchi EA, Almeida DR, Fragata Filho AA, Moreira Mda C, Xavier SS, Oliveira Junior WA, Dias JC; Sociedade Brasileira de Cardiologia. I Diretriz Latino Americana para o Diagnóstico e Tratamento da Cardiopatia Chagásica. [I Latin American guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of Chagas cardiomyopathy]. *Arq Bras Cardiol* 2011; 97: 1-48.
- [16] David M. Engman, Northwestern University, Department of Pathology, 303 E. Chicago Ave. Ward 6-140.
- [17] Tanowitz, HB.; Kirchoff, LV.; Simon, D.; Morris, SA.; Weiss, LM.; Wittner, M. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. Vol. 5. 1992. p. 400-419.
- [18] Miles, MA.; Feliciangeli, MD.; de Arias, AR. *BMJ*. Vol. 326. 2003. p. 1444-1448.
- [19] Bocchi EA, Bestetti RB, Scanavacca MI, Cunha Neto E, Issa VS. Chronic Chagas Heart Disease Management. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 2017 Sep;70(12):1510–24.

- [20] Woody NC, Woody HB (1955) American trypanosomiasis (Chagas' disease); first indigenous case in the United States. *JAMA* 159: 676–677. 2. Kirchhoff LV, Neva FA (1985) Chagas' disease in Latin American immigrants. *JAMA* 254: 3058–3060
- [21] Andrews, NW.; Abrams, CK.; Slatin, SL.; Griffiths, G. *Cell*. Vol. 61. 1990. p. 1277-1287.
- [22] Schmunis GA. Epidemiology of Chagas disease in non-endemic countries: the role of international migration. *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz*. 2007; 102 (Suppl 1):75–85
- [23] Gascon J, Bern C, Pinazo MJ. Chagas disease in Spain, the United States, and other non-endemic countries. *Acta Trop*. 2010; 115:22–27.
- [24] Kirchhoff LV. Epidemiology of American trypanosomiasis (Chagas disease). *Advances in parasitology*. 2011; 75:1–18
- [25] Jiang Y, Xin S, Ma Y, Zhang H, Yang X, Yang Y. Low Prevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in Sheep and Isolation of a Viable Strain from Edible Mutton from Central China. *Pathogens*. 2023 Jun 14;12(6):827
- [26] Dubey, J.P. *Toxoplasmosis of Animals and Humans*, 3rd ed.; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA; Taylor & Francis Group: Abingdon, UK, 2022; pp. 1–542.
- [27] Havelaar AH, Kemmeren JM, Kortbeek LM. 2007. Disease burden of congenital toxoplasmosis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 44(11), 1467–1474.
- [28] Jeffrey D. Kravetz, MD, Daniel G. Federman, MD, *Toxoplasmosis in pregnancy*, *The American Journal of Medicine* (2005); 118:212–216.
- [29] Mombro M, Perathoner C, Leone A, et al. Congenital toxoplasmosis: assessment of risk to newborns in confirmed and uncertain maternal infection. *Eur J Pediatr*. 2003; 162:703–706..
- [30] Robert-Gangneux F, Darde ML. 2012. Epidemiology of and diagnostic strategies for toxoplasmosis. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 25(2), 264–296.
- [31] Markell EK, John DT, Krotoski WA. *Toxoplasma gondii*. In: Markell and Voges's *Medical Parasitology*. 8th ed. Philadelphia, Pennsylvania: W.B. Saunders; 1999: 161–171.
- [32] Montoya JG. Laboratory diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection and toxoplasmosis. *J Infect Dis* 2002; 185(Suppl 1):S73–82.
- [33] Wilson M, Remington JS, Clavet C, et al. Evaluation of six commercial kits for detection of human immunoglobulin M antibodies to *Toxoplasma gondii*. *J Clin Microbiol* 1997; 35:3112–5.
- [34] Foulon W, Villena I, Stray-Pedersen B, et al. Treatment of toxoplasmosis during pregnancy: a multicenter study of impact on fetal transmission and children's sequelae at age 1 year. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1999; 180: 410–5.
- [35] Montoya JG, Remington JS. *Clinical Practice: Management of Toxoplasma gondii Infection during Pregnancy*, *Clinical Practice*. 2008 Aug 15;47(4):554–66.
- [36] Yuan R, Huang J, Zhang X, Ruan S. Modeling the Transmission Dynamics of Clonorchiasis in Foshan, China. *Sci Rep*. 2018 Oct 11;8(1):15176.
- [37] Gowda, C. Recognizing clonorchiasis: a foodborne illness leading to significant hepatobiliary disease. *Clin. Liver Dis*. 6;2014: 44–46.
- [38] Qian MB, Utzinger J, Keiser J, Zhou XN. Clonorchiasis. *Lancet*. 2016;387(10020):800–10.
- [39] Santucci C, Bonelli P, Peruzzi A, Fancellu A, Marras V, Carta A, et al. Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy). *Pathogens*. 2020 Oct 30;9(11):907.
- [40] Thompson, R.C.A. Chapter Two—Biology and Systematics of *Echinococcus*. In *Advances in Parasitology*; Thompson, R.C.A., Deplazes, P., Lymbery, A.J., Eds.; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2017; Volume 95, pp. 65–109.

- [41] Agudelo Higueta, N.I.; Brunetti, E.; McCloskey, C. Cystic echinococcosis. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 2016, *54*, 518–523.
- [42] Agudelo Higueta NI, Brunetti E, McCloskey C. Cystic Echinococcosis. Kraft CS, editor. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2016 Mar;54(3):518–23.
- [43] Sadjjadi SM, Mikaeili F, Karamian M, Maraghi S, Sadjjadi FS, ShariatTorbaghan S, Kia EB. 2013. Evidence that the *Echinococcus granulosus* G6 genotype has an affinity for the brain in humans. *Int J Parasitol* 43:875– 877.
- [44] Craig PS, McManus DP, Lightowers MW, Chabalgoity JA, Garcia HH, Gavidia CM, Gilman RH, Gonzalez AE, Lorca M, Naquira C, Nieto A, Schantz PM. 2007. Prevention and control of cystic echinococcosis. *Lancet Infect Dis* 7:385–394